

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Methyl Isobutyl Ketone by Manganese (III) Sulphate

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Oxidation of methyl isobutyl ketone with Mn(III) sulphate in aqueous acetic acid is first order with respect to the oxidant and the ketone. The rate is independent of acidity and solvent composition. Addition of Mn(II) does not alter the rate. The activation parameters for the oxidation and enolisation reactions have been evaluated. The rate of enolisation, under similar conditions, is less than that of oxidation. A mechanism involving a direct attack on the keto-form by Mn(III) explains the observed data.

The conclusion of Drummond and Waters¹ that cyclohexanone is oxidised by Mn(III) via its enol form was challenged by Littler² who showed that Mn(III) sulphate oxidises cyclohexanone at a rate faster than its enolisation. Recently we showed that oxidation of acetone also involved an attack on the keto-form³. The present paper reports the result of oxidation of methyl isobutyl ketone by manganese (III) sulphate.

EXPERIMENTAL

(i) *Materials* : Methyl isobutyl ketone (B.D.H.) was fractionated before use. Acetic acid (99.5% B.D.H.) was distilled over chromic acid. All other chemicals used were of extra pure quality. Manganese (III) sulphate was prepared by the method described by Vogel⁴.

(ii) *Kinetic measurements* : Unless otherwise stated the reactions were carried out in 20% acetic acid solution and at 35° ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). Sufficient excess of manganese (II) were added to prevent disproportionation and subsequent hydrolysis of manganese (III).

Throughout the investigation the concentration of the ketone was kept at sufficiently large excess to ensure that the rate of reduction of Mn(III) is proportional to the oxidation of the ketone itself and not to the rate of destruction of any reactive intermediate.

Reactions were followed by quenching aliquots, withdrawn at known intervals of time, in slight excess of ferrous ammonium sulphate and estimating the residual iron (II) by titrating it against standardised cerium (IV).

(iii) *Rates of enolisation* : Enolisation rates were measured by bromination method.

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1. A. Y. Drummond and W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 497.
2. J. S. Littler, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 832.
3. K. K. Banerji, P. Nath and G. V. Bakore, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1970, **8**, 337.
4. A. I. Vogel, "A Text book of quantitative inorganic Chemistry", Longmans, Green and Co. Ltd., London (1964), 327.

The rates of bromination were followed by adding bromine to a thermostated solution of the ketone in acetic acid containing suitable amounts of sulphuric acid. Aliquots were withdrawn, at known intervals of time, acidity adjusted by sodium bicarbonate and bromine left unreacted was determined iodometrically.

RESULTS

Induced reduction of mercuric chloride : Mn (III) oxidation of methyl isobutyl ketone induces reduction of mercuric chloride. This indicates the formation of a reducing intermediate, i.e., a free radical.

Product Analysis : To identify the products, the reaction was carried out in aqueous solution. The reduction of Mn(III) sulphate by an excess of methyl isobutyl ketone results in the formation of acetic acid and isobutyraldehyde. The products were detected by their characteristic spot tests⁵.

Rate laws : When the ketone is in excess the rate of disappearance of Mn(III) followed first order rate laws. Further the rate constant is independent of the initial concentration of the oxidant (Table 1). The order with respect to the ketone is also one (Table 2).

TABLE 1

Variation of rate with concentration of Mn(III)
 [Ketone] : $6.1 \times 10^{-2} M$ [Mn(II)] : $0.21 M$ [H₂SO₄] : $2.0 M$

[Mn(III)] $\times 10^3 M$	2.14	3.21	4.28	6.42	8.56	10.70
$10^4 k_1$ (sec. ⁻¹)	1.12	1.16	1.19	1.19	1.23	1.19

TABLE 2

Variation of rate with concentration of the ketone
 [Mn(III)] : $4.28 \times 10^{-3} M$ [Mn(II)] : $0.21 M$ [H₂SO₄] : $2.0 M$

[Ketone] $\times 10^2 M$	6.10	9.15	12.20	18.30	24.40	30.50
$10^4 k_1$ (sec. ⁻¹)	1.19	1.76	2.40	3.50	4.76	5.90
$10^3 k_1 / [\text{ketone}]$	1.95	1.92	1.97	1.92	1.95	1.93

Under the condition of constant ionic strength the rate of oxidation is practically independent of acidity (Table 3).

TABLE 3

Acid dependence of the reaction rate
 [Ketone] : $6.1 \times 10^{-3} M$ [Mn(III)] : $4.28 \times 10^{-3} M$
 [Mn(II)] : $0.11 M$ [NaHSO₄ + H₂SO₄] : $5.0 M$

[H ₂ SO ₄] M	2.00	2.50	3.00	3.50	4.00	5.00
$10^4 k_1$ (sec. ⁻¹)	1.19	1.19	1.19	1.23	1.19	1.19

Effect of manganese (II) : Addition of manganese (II) sulphate ($0.05-0.5 M$) does not affect the oxidation rate. Similar result was observed in the oxidation of cyclohexanone with manganese (III) sulphate⁶.

5. F. Feigl, "Spot Tests in Organic Analysis", Elsevier Publishing Co., Amsterdam, 1966.

6. T. J. Kemp and W. A. Waters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 339.

Similarly changes in the proportion of acetic acid (20–60%) has no appreciable effect on the oxidation rate.

Effect of temperature : Data in Table 4 summarize the effect of temperature on the reaction rate. The specific rate constant, k , is obtained from the relation : $k = k_1/[\text{ketone}]$.

TABLE 4

Effect of temperature
[Mn(III)] : $4.28 \times 10^{-3} M$ [Mn(II)] : $0.21 M$ [H₂SO₄] : $2.0 M$

Temp. °C	$10^3 k$ l.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	ΔH^* k.cals mole ⁻¹	ΔS^* e.u.
30	1.07	22 ± 1	-0.6
35	1.95	ΔF^* at 35°	
40	3.52	22.5 k.cals mole ⁻¹	
45	6.17		

The plot of $\log k$ against inverse of temperature gave a straight line. Arrhenius equation is, therefore, valid for this reaction. The activation parameters have been calculated in the usual way.

Rates of bromination : The bromination of methyl isobutyl ketone is of first order with respect to each of the ketone and hydrogen ion, but of zero order with respect to bromine. The rate of bromination divided by concentrations of the ketone and hydrogen ions gives k_2 (l.mole⁻¹sec⁻¹). Table 5 records the values of k_2 at different proportions of acetic acid-water. The rate of bromination was studied at different temperatures and activation parameters were evaluated (Table 6).

TABLE 5

Rate of bromination

Acetic acid %	20	30	50	80
$10^4 k_2$ (l.mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹)	2.88	2.98	3.07	6.03

TABLE 6

Effect of temperature on the rate of bromination

Solvent : 50% Acetic acid (v/v)

Temp. °C	$10^4 k_2$ l.mole ⁻¹ sec. ⁻¹	ΔH^* k.cals mole ⁻¹	ΔS^* e.u.
30	1.77	20 ± 1	-10
35	3.07	ΔF^* at 35°	
40	5.13	23 ± 1 k.cals mole ⁻¹	

DISCUSSION

Manganese (II) is known to affect the rate of oxidation of several compounds^{6,7}, where the oxidising species is Mn(IV) and this has been attributed to its effect on the following equilibrium :

Absence of any effect of Mn(II) on the rate of oxidation suggests that in this case, Mn(III) is the only oxidising species.

Enolisation of methyl isobutyl ketone is an acid catalysed reaction whereas the oxidation is independent of acidity. Furthermore, the enolisation rate is increased with proportion of acetic acid in the solvent while oxidation is unaffected by such changes. Thus the kinetics of the two reactions are quite different and enolisation is not likely to be involved in the oxidation process.

The rate of enolisation of methyl isobutyl ketone in 20% acetic acid solution, at 35° is 2.88×10^{-4} l.mole⁻¹sec⁻¹, whereas the specific rate constant, k , for the oxidation under identical conditions is 19.5×10^{-4} l.mole⁻¹sec⁻¹. If enolisation was to precede oxidation, the oxidation rate in the limit could be equal to the rate of enolisation, but could have never exceeded it. This, therefore, clearly proves that oxidation of methyl isobutyl ketone by manganese(III) sulphate proceed by a direct attack on the keto-form.

Thus it appears that a mechanism similar to that proposed for ethyl methyl ketone—Mn(III) reaction⁸, i.e., an attack of Mn(III) sulphate complex on the ketone to first form a reversible complex and its slow decomposition to give a free radical satisfactorily accounts for the observed kinetics of the reaction.

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